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LINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF CONCEPT "FRIENDSHIP"

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the linguistic characterizations of the notion of "friendship", focusing in particular on some English-Uzbek cultural encounters. In this paper we revisit the question whether these conceptualizations are individual or culture-specific and attempt to answer this question through the linguistic analysis of the concept "friendship", and its Uzbek dictionary and translation equivalents

The cross-cultural study of the words defining social values are of particular importance in interdisciplinary contexts, as the knowledge of their culture-specific semantic as well as discursive characteristics contributes to a better understanding of how people think and act in a society. One of the important terms in cognitive linguistics and linguaculture is the term "concept". In this regard, the key point in the cognitive nature of the concept serves as vice-monetary function. It should be noted that the term "concept" was used as a synonym for the concept. In our view, is synonymous with the use of two terms due to interlingua lexical equivalence of these two words. Translated from the Latin concept's meaning idea, the notion of

«semantic meaning of the name (sign), i.e. the content of the concept, the volume of which is the object (denotation) of the name» [1]. It attracted the attention of many researchers, interested in issues related to concept and the property of the human mind. After analyzing a wide variety of issues on the nature of the concept, scientists have come to the certain conclusions concerning concept, which is analysed thoroughly in this paper. As we know, the concept is not only based on lingvocultural field of the hierarchical system of units but also it has a common value and reflecting system of relevant cultures. In recent years, Uzbekistan has increased the number of studies on study concepts, and this linguistic analysis of the

linguacultural concept of “friendship” (do’sstlik) in both English and Uzbek languages is the result of these elaborated studies.

MATERIALS REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY
Dedicated linguistic area mainly forms the conceptual core of the concept of Friendship (Do’sstlik) that is because the “friendship” in all languages is the central and saint mean of human qualities. Due to the fact that the majority of dictionary words as linguistic interpretation unit is basically the same in the three languages studied, we will consider the dictionary definition based on the English language. However, all cases of lexicographical discrepancies in interpretations of the language will be considered separately. [2]

Several western scholars, such as Risager highlights an important characteristic of linguaculture in relation to constancy and variability, stating that they should be taken relatively, as the boundaries between the two ends of the continuum are not fixed. Additionally, she argues, “linguaculture is both absolute and relational. One can study linguaculture of a language “in itself”, or one can include another language and carry out an investigation of what happens in the meeting between languages ...” [3]. In other words, linguaculture thus defined deals with “that which is language specific, ... focusing in particular on linguistic differences”. This is precisely the angle that complements neatly the contrastive analytical approach which we adopt in this research initiative, specifically its more recent developments and innovations [4].

We particularly concur with Wierzbicka on her stance “that meaning is what language is primarily about and that the study of language should first and primarily be

conducted through the prism of meaning”. Wierzbicka here essentially draws from Leibniz, specifically his claim that “... amongst the words, some are frequently used and serve as auxiliary to the others”, referring to this phenomenon as “the alphabet of human thoughts”. [5]

Following this line of argumentation, therefore, our intention here is to “identify and describe culture-specific elements of meaning” (Gladkova and Larina 2018b: 718), “... cultural ideas’ that penetrate language and get encoded in the meanings of lexemes, morphemes and grammatical constructions ...” [6]. Wierzbicka refers to this phenomenon as cultural keywords, which are words particularly important and revealing in a given culture. She states that “[t]here is a very close link between the life of a society and the lexicon of the language spoken by it” [7]. Sociolinguists also develop this idea. As Smakman notes, “... approaching culture through values entails capturing how people in various cultures value fundamental aspects in life such as religion, happiness, materialism, gender roles, freedom of choice, self-expression, tradition, and authority” [8].

Based on the above concept of structure, we consider verbalization of the concept Friendship (Do’sstlik) at lexical level. Represented keywords of studying concept Friendship (Do’sstlik) will be the foundation of our lexical analysis. The analysis is performed on the material of the dictionary definitions of a number of dictionaries, are also used associative dictionaries and thesaurus, which allows to identify associative links Friendship (Do’sstlik) , which play an important role in the formation of both the conceptual and the value of the concept components. The

analysis showed that the conceptual core of the Friendship (Do'stlik) shown cognitive-conceptual signs, which can be roughly divided into linguistic Friendship (Do'stlik) and philosophical and literary areas. Note that the conceptual cognitive symptoms occurring in these areas, as well as the zones themselves, may be reflected in one or two in all the languages. For example, a linguistic area is represented in all languages, while the philosophical and literary area on the lexical level in the Uzbek language is not reflected.

DATA AND ANALYSIS

The origin of "friendship" came from Old English frēond, of Germanic origin and it is related to Dutch vriend and German Freund, from an Indo-European root meaning 'to love'. There are some chunks belonging to the concept we are working on:

- be friends with means be (or become) on good or affectionate terms with (someone);
- a friend at court means a person in a position to use their influence on one's behalf;
- a friend in need is a friend indeed means a person who helps at a difficult time is a person who you can really rely on;
- friends in high places means people in senior positions who are able and willing to use their influence on one's behalf;
- my honourable friend means used to address or refer to another member of one's own party in the House of Commons;
- my learned friend means used by a barrister or solicitor in court to address or refer to another barrister or solicitor;
- my noble friend used to address or refer to another member of one's own party in the House of Lords;
- my Right Honourable friend means used to address or refer to another member of one's

own party in the House of Commons who is also a privy counselor.

Now we try to give synonyms for this concept:

- a) companion, soul mate, intimate, confidante, confidant, familiar, alter ego, second self, playmate, playfellow, classmate, schoolmate, workmate;
- b) ally, associate;
- c) sister, brother;
- d) best friend, kindred spirit, bosom buddy, bosom friend;
- e) pal, chum, sidekick, crony, main man, mate, buddy, bud, amigo, compadre, homeboy, homegirl, homie;
- f) compeer.

We are going to write the list of antonyms below:

Enemy (enemies) is a person who is actively opposed or hostile to someone or something;

- a hostile nation or its armed forces, especially in time of war the enemy shot down four helicopter;
- (as modifier) enemy aircraft is a thing that harms or weakens something else routine is the enemy of art;
- be one's own worst enemy.

The origin of this word came from Middle English: from Old French enemi, from Latin inimicus, from in- 'not' + amicus 'friend'

Linguistic "Friendship" concept content area is mainly represented by the following values of the taken word:

- 1) the emotions or conduct of friends; the state of being friends a relationship between friends she formed close friendships with women:
 - a friendly feeling or emotion (MWCD; LDCE; CODCE);
 - kindness or help given to someone (OALD);

2) A friendship is a relationship between two or more friends:

- a state of mutual trust and support between allied nations (OALD; CIDE);
- a relationship between friends: She formed close friendships with women (MWCD); (OALD);
- a state of supporting a cause, organization, or country by giving financial or other help; For example: "I was thunderstruck by my friend's words. We had only been a few hours in Devonshire, and that he should give up an investigation, which he had begun so brilliantly was quite incomprehensible to me. Not a word more could I draw from him until we were back at the trainer's house. The colonel and the inspector were awaiting us in the parlour. "My friend and I return to town by the night-express," said Holmes. "We have had a charming little breath of your beautiful Dartmoor air." [9]

3) A friendship is feeling which is needed in trouble. In this meaning of the friendship appears as a question, saying, idiom, saying, aphorism:

- a person who is not an enemy or opponent; an ally. (MWCD),(OALD);
- a familiar or helpful thing. (CODCE; OALD; CIDE);

4) a member of the Religious Society of Friends; a Quaker (CIDE);

5) an acquaintance or a stranger one comes across (used as a polite form of address or in ironic reference): "My friends, let me introduce myself."

"My friend Dr. Watson made that suggestion to me as we came down. If so, it would tell against this man Simpson." [9]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It should be noted that in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language fixed meaning as "do'stlik, qadrdonlik,

birodarlik" and Uzbeks thinks that this feeling is seemed stronger if one's friend is from one of his family members, for example, "Ona - eng yaqin do'st", or "Ota-onang va jigarlaringdan boshqasiga ishonma", in contrast to English, in which the friendship has the meaning of someone who you know well and like, but who is not related to you" [10]

As already noted, the concept of Friendship (Do'stlik) is so complex, multidimensional, mental education, which, exploring its deep conceptual structure, it is advisable to consider this concept in terms of the conceptual sphere. As is known, concept - an ordered, structured set of individual and collective knowledge, the units of which are the concepts. As rightly pointed out by V.A.Maslov, "language is determined by the wealth of not only the richness of vocabulary and grammatical features, but also the wealth of the world concept, concept, which formed the national language personality" [11]. The focus of this section focuses on building fragment Friendship concept sphere Friendship (Do'stlik) on the basis of linguistic zone data, which forms the core of our concept of the test at the lexical level.

In the process of interpretation of the dictionary definitions of the correlation values found "friendship" - "relationship" - "feeling", characterized by metonymic relations. These values are inherent in the lexical units, which serve as the name of the relevant concepts. This indicates that in at the lexical level of the language system, you can talk about the formation concept Friendship (Do'stlik). However, the nature of the interaction of these concepts, their deep structure revealed in their textual realization, and therefore when the concept

of the structure of the study is necessary to refer to the text, in particular to the artistic, aphorisms and journalistic, which act as a "transfer of value orientations from person to person. All this allows us to consider the text as a cognitive process associated "with a specific selection of cognitive operations or their preferred use in the construction and interpretation of texts of different types".

The concept of having friends has been around for centuries. It is a natural part of one's life and yet, it is not until recently that scientist's has acknowledged it as a scientific topic. This study aims to investigate what it entails to be a friend today and which types of friendships exists, in contrast to the historical definitions and theoretical discussions addressed in Ray Pahl's book *On Friendship* (2000). Two focus group interviews were conducted, with one male and one female group, to find out how the concepts of friendship, acquaintance and best friend are defined

today. The concepts on how to become friends together with what impact Facebook has had on friendship today was also discussed in the interviews [12]

CONCLUSION

To sum up, the analysis of the interaction concept "Friendship" revealed a number of cognitive and conceptual features of the conceptual, emotional, imaginative, value character, which together determine the originality of the concept sphere in every language. When the mind makes a generalization such as the concept of tree, it extracts similarities from numerous examples; the simplification enables higher-level thinking. Therefore, the meaning of "concept" is explored in cognitive science, metaphysics, and philosophy of mind. The use of concepts is necessary to cognitive processes such as categorization, memory, decision making, learning, and inference. The relevant peculiarities of the concept will be further explored in the context of diplomatic discourse.

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